

EXPRESSION OF HUMAN APPEARANCE IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH ZOONYM COMPONENT

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Abstract. *In this article, analysis has been made of French phraseological units with a zoonymic component to describe a person's appearance from different angles. Phraseologisms with a zoonym component have been analyzed as one of the most expressive means of expressing physical characteristics of a person, facial features, cleanliness of a person's appearance and attractiveness. It has also been found that such phraseologies are verbalized mainly through universal zoonyms that have a negative connotation.*

Keywords: *appearance, zoomorph, zoonyms, phraseological units with zoonym component, zoomorphic code.*

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ ОБРАЗА ЧЕЛОВЕКА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИМИ ЕДИНИЦАМИ С ЗООНИМИЧЕСКИМ КОМПОНЕНТОМ

Аннотация. *В данной статье проведен анализ французских фразеологизмов с зоонимическим компонентом для описания внешности человека с разных сторон. Проанализированы фразеологизмы с зоонимическим компонентом как одно из наиболее выразительных средств выражения физических характеристик человека, черт лица, чистоты внешности человека и привлекательности. Выявлено также, что такие фразеологии вербализуются в основном через универсальные зоонимы, имеющие отрицательную коннотацию.*

Ключевые слова: *внешний вид, зооморфа, зоонимы, фразеологизмы с зоонимическим компонентом, зооморфный код.*

Introduction

Human appearance is essentially social in nature. All his mental characteristics and the sources of development of creative activity characteristic of him are definitely reflected in the surrounding social environment, that is, in society. A person's appearance is reflected in his social life in a way that is related to his real existence. In this sense, the appearance of a person's appearance consists of the process of acquiring social experience that occurs in interaction with people. As a result, a person's mental characteristics, moral qualities, character, volitional qualities, interests, beliefs and worldview are formed.

The contribution of phraseological units to describe the appearance of a person and reflect it in the language is significant. Linguistic meaning formation is a unique complex process. In the formation of meaning, the reflection of the important features - signs of the object in reality is not a simple process, but these features should be important from the point of view of human social activity and experience. More precisely, such significance arises on the basis of social experience. Psycholinguists did not make a mistake by defining meaning as a "transformed form of human activity", because the characteristics of the perceived object become visible and different in the process of human social activity [Sh. Safarov: 175.].

Materials

Here, it is worth noting that the zoomorphic code of the French language is an interesting phenomenon that reveals the unique features of the worldview of the owners of the French

language and culture. Although this code is universal, it is distinguished by its national identity. In particular, animals are considered to be one of the appropriate linguistic signs of certain human qualities that reflect the experience of speakers of this language, acquiring a symbolic meaning.

In modern linguistics, the study of lexical-semantic features of zoonyms is conducted in different directions. Mainly, special attention is paid to the semantic structure of animal names. Phraseological units with an animal component are of particular interest in order to determine the specific features of the zoonymic cultural code in the French language. In their work, scientists use different terms to include animal components in phraseological units. For example, L.N. Gishkaeva uses the term zoonymic component of a phraseological unit [L. Gishkaeva: 20.], A.O. Kubasova works on the basis of the concept of zoolexema [A. Kubasova: 24.], S.A. Androsova calls the components of animal names zoonyms [A. Androsova: 220.]

Methods

According to their structure, phraseological units in the language can show a very diverse world. In particular, the semantic links between their structural elements are distinguished by expressing different relationships. The words included in such units retain their independence of meaning to a certain degree, that is, to a strong or weak degree. [Suvonova N.N., Daliyeva L.B.: 69]. Most of the French phraseological units with a zoonym component express a human character. Phraseological units with a zoonym component are represented by various structural models. For example, animal, bird, fish, insect, and reptile contain components of names and serve to reflect human characteristics.

Phraseological units with a zoonym component is a multifaceted phenomenon associated with social and psychological characteristics of human personality. Such units are compounds with different degrees of coherence and semantic integrity, based on the experience of observing the behavior and habits of animals, they mean reactions, appearance, etc. [F. Guketlova: 8.]

Figurative character of phraseological units is revealed by interlinking its literal meaning. This phenomenon shows that the perception of the speakers based on the phraseological unit differs depending on their intellectual and general education level, as well as individual characteristics [YU. G. Sinelnikov, S.A. Androsova: 50.]. It is important for understanding the world to identify the stereotypes and norms of the national culture in the study of the system of language signs, to understand the specific features of the perception of the world. Because "comparison of its specific characteristics with "inhuman" characteristics is accepted as "standards of human characteristics" [V. N. Telia: 241].

Discussion

Most Phraseological units with a zoonym component are comparative phrases. The members of such phraseology are interconnected by the conjunctions *tel*, *aussi... que*, *autant... que*, *plus... que*, *moins... que*, *comme*: "*poilu comme un singe*" (very hairy); "*gros comme une vache*" (huge as a cow, very fat). In this study, special attention is paid to the analysis of phraseological units, because they have a potential image quality. In phraseological units of this type, it is necessary to pay attention to the meaning of individual elements that make up the figurative "core" of phraseological units. A person's appearance means a set of unique features that give an impression of his appearance. Some scientists distinguish only anatomical features, such as completeness, strength and height [J. H. Gergokova: 18.]. It also has functional (voice, facial expressions, walking) and social (clothes, jewelry) features [M. M. Robertus: 16.].

During the analysis of phraseological units with a zoonym component from this point of view, it became clear that they serve to reveal the following aspects of a person's appearance:

Aspects of appearance	French phraseological units	Uzbek meaning
Body condition	<i>gros comme une baleine</i>	kitdek semiz
Facial features	<i>avoir les yeux de chèvre morte</i>	o'lik echkining ko'ziga ega bo'lmoq, xijolat tortgan ko'rinishga ega bo'lmoq
Describe the dress	<i>être propre comme un lapin</i>	juda ozoda bo'lmoq
Walking	<i>être comme un éléphant dans un magasin de porcelaine(s)</i>	juda qo'pol bo'lmoq, chayqalmoq, lapanglab yurmoq
The level of attractiveness	<i>être moche (laid) comme un pou</i>	bitga o'xshab xunuk bo'lmoq

Body condition

Animal names such as "whale", "cow", "pig" and "quail" are used to express the fatness of a person: "gros comme une baleine" ("fat like a whale") "gras comme un cochon" ("fat as a pig") - "very fat". The zoonyms "cat" and "dog" are widely used to describe emaciation: "maigre comme un chat de gouttière" (as thin as a house cat), "maigre comme un chien fou" ("as thin as a mad dog") - "very thin in, as thin as a stick". French phraseological units use the word tique to express the characteristics of a short person: "ne pas être plus grand qu'un tique". For example, in literary texts, they are the same makes sense as:

"Mais, sur mon honneur, le voilà devenu aussi gras qu'un cochon" (De Las Cases E. Mémorial de Sainte-Hélène. 1963. p. 321). / *Honestly, he's fat as a pig. (Translation by the authors)*

Facial features. Through the results of the analysis, it was determined that the following zoonyms are means of describing the appearance of a person:

- Animal names such as le rat (rat) and le crabe (crab) are symbols of an ugly face: "avoir la face de rat" (to be ugly with a rat's face).

- The components "rat" and "goat" are used to express the negative nature of the human gaze: "avalier un rat" (to look displeased), "avoir les yeux de chèvre morte" ("to look into the eyes of a dead goat") – "to have an embarrassed look".

- Phraseological units with the component "frog" give a positive assessment of a person's gaze: "faire un œil de crapaud mort d'amour" (literal translation: "to look with the eyes of a frog dying of love") - love to to look with 'la eyes'.

- Cochon (pig) means the small and small size of the eye: "avoir l'œil de cochon" - "to have small and deep-set eyes"

Describe the dress. It should be noted that the word le lapin (rabbit) refers to the clean appearance of the clothes worn by a person: "être propre comme un lapin" (to be very neat). The analysis showed that animals such as "monkey", "bear", "lice", "pig", "crow" and "duck" are used to represent carelessly chosen clothes, disorder and bad taste. For example:

"avoir l'air d'un singe botté" (to be a bastard/like a monkey);

"être sale comme un pou"

"aller comme un pardessus à un canard" (to walk with a dirty head).

Such phraseology is also often found in literary texts: *J'en viens à toi, Moulu. Tu es un nid à poux, ça ne peut pas durer ... tu es sale comme un cochon!*" (Sartre J.-P. *La Mort dans l'âme*. Livre de poche, 1962. r. 64]. / *I came for you, Moulu. You are a nest of lice, it cannot go on like this... you are dirty as a pig* (Translation by the authors)

Walking. The word *le zebre* (zebra), which is a part of the phraseological unit, expresses a person who always walks fast when describing his appearance, as if he is hurrying somewhere: "*courir comme un zebre*" (to come running in a hurry). Animal names such as "elephant", "frog", "crow", "pig" and "duck" are used to describe rough walking:

- "*être comme un éléphant dans un magasin de porcelaine(s)*" - to be clumsy;
- "*se dandiner comme un canard*" - quack like a duck;

Phraseological units with the component *la tortue* (tortoise) mean that a person walks slowly: "*aller comme une tortue*" - to walk like a turtle.

The word *le serpent* (snake) is used to describe crawling:

- "*(se) glisser comme un serpent (or une couleuvre)*" - (to crawl like a snake).

1. *Le crabe* (the crab) component phraseological units are used to describe a person's walk, meaning a wobbly walk:

- 2. - "*marcher en crabe*" - to stagger.

3. Examples of the use of these expressions in artistic texts are: "*Ils se deratent, ils se decaassent! C'est du sobre, des gens qui boiront de l'eau... Ils current comme des zebres*" [Céline L.-F. *Mort à crédit*. Gallimard, 1985. p. 336]. / *They are angry, they are dispersing! It's vigilance, people who are looking for water... they are running like zebras*" (authors' translation).

4. "*Il pensa à la métaphore de l'éléphant qu'on lâche dans un magasin de porcelaine et il voyait de précieuses porcelaines écrasées sous des pattes énormes.*" (Curtis J. L. *La quarantaine*. Rocher Eds Du, 1989. p.66). "*He recalled the metaphor of an elephant entering a china shop, and before his eyes stood pieces of precious china crushed by gigantic feet*" (authors' translation).

5. Artus. - *Le diable! Il se glisse comme une couleuvre. Je ne sais jamais où le prendre*" (Cocteau J. *Les chevaliers de la table ronde*. Gallimard, 1937. p. 24). / "*Artus. - He's a real devil! He's slipping away anyway. I don't even know how to catch him*" (translated by the authors).

The level of attractiveness. In French, phraseological units with the zoonym "dog" are used to express the characteristics of an attractive person: "*avoir du chien*" - to be attractive.

According to the results of the analysis, it was found that the frequency of use of zoonim to describe the external appearance is as follows:

№	Zoonyms	Forms of appearance of the human figure:				
		Physical condition	Refreshment	Dress and neatness	Behavior	external attractiveness
1.	<i>bear</i>			+		
2.	<i>quail</i>	+				

3.	<i>zebra</i>				+	
4.	<i>goat</i>		+			+
5.	<i>pig</i>	+	+	+	+	
6.	<i>elephant</i>				+	
7.	<i>snake</i>				+	
8.	<i>dog</i>	+				+
9.	<i>rat</i>		+			
10.	<i>mite</i>	+				
11.	<i>whale</i>	+				
12.	<i>monkey</i>			+		+
13.	<i>cat</i>	+				
14.	<i>duck</i>			+	+	
15.	<i>crow</i>			+	+	
16.	<i>crab</i>		+			
17.	<i>frog</i>				+	+
18.	<i>rabbit</i>			+		
19.	<i>cow</i>	+				
20.	<i>turtle</i>				+	

Conclusion

Also, the conducted studies show that a large number of French phraseological units with a zoonym component affect different aspects of human appearance, and they are generally universal. Phraseologisms with zoonym components such as "whale", "cow", "pig", "quail", "cat", "dog", "tick" are used to express the characteristics of a person's physique. The components "rat", "crab", "goat", "pig" act as symbols of different facial features of a person. "Clothes and cleanliness" feature is taken from the point of view of neatness or dirtiness of people's appearance. In this case, zoonyms such as "rabbit", "monkey", "bear", "lice", "pig", "crow", "duck" are characterized. "Worm" is used to describe behavior. The zoonyms "zebra", "elephant", "frog", "crow", "pig", "duck", "turtle", "snake" represent different types of walking. French phraseological units with the components "dog", "monkey", "goat", "frog", "lice" describe different levels of attractiveness of a person. It should be noted that many phraseological units with a zoonym component in French have a negative evaluation feature. A number of animal species such as "goat", "pig", "dog", "rat", "crab", "frog", "lice", "crow", "duck" and "monkey" can be a representation of the characteristics. Undoubtedly, in the selection of a certain zoomorphic component in the phraseological units, the images specific to each animal in the linguistic mind of the speakers play an important role.

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